

Technical Paper:

Overview of Profilometry-based Indentation Plastometry and its Industrial Usage

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Abstract

This paper includes a review of the current state-of-the-art in a technique for extracting the (quasi-static) stress-strain relationship of a metallic sample from an indentation experiment, as well as an industrial case study using the technique to map the stress-strain properties of a forged part. The technique, called profilometry-based indentation plastometry (PIP), uses a large (either 1 mm or 0.5 mm radius) spherical indenter to create a residual indent under relatively high applied loads (kN range). The indent profile is measured, and iterative finite element method (FEM) simulation of the indentation is carried out to converge on the true stress-strain curve of the indented material (with the indent profile as the target outcome). Commercial products are now available that automatically complete indentation, profilometry and convergence upon Voce plasticity parameter values, which describe the full stress-strain curve within a few minutes. The review covers the technique's advantages as an indentation-based technique, firstly in the mapping of samples and secondly in giving insight into the direction and sense of anisotropy from the breakdown in radial symmetry. The case study demonstrates the application of the technique in both of these areas for characterising a forged part, comparing the results from PIP to conventional uniaxial testing. It is shown that the scale of PIP unveils local inhomogeneity unable to be detected by tensile testing, where these differences can be linked to the prior plastic strains introduced during forging. Additionally, anisotropy is detected by PIP relating to aligned FeNiAl precipitates that give a sense of the strength and direction of the anisotropy.

Keywords: Indentation; Stress-strain curves; Profilometry; Inverse FEM.

1. Introduction

Attempts to extract meaningful plasticity characteristics from indentation tests on metals have a long history. These characteristics are fully described by the relationship between the applied stress and the resultant plastic strain, which is conventionally obtained via a uniaxial tensile test, or in some cases via a uniaxial compression test. However, while this relationship also dictates the outcome of an indentation test, inferring the former from the latter is far from simple. The stress

and strain fields are naturally much more complex, and evolve substantially, during an indentation operation, compared with the situation during a uniaxial test. However, progress has been made recently and a viable methodology has been developed. Known as profilometry-based indentation plastometry (PIP), the methodology involves measurement of the residual indent profile and then iterative finite element modelling (FEM) of the indentation operation, to infer the stress-strain relationship that is most consistent with that profile. While this is relatively simple in principle, the methodology must be optimized in several respects if accurate stress-strain curves are to be obtained in an efficient and robust manner. It may also be noted that most early attempts to implement this kind of approach were based on use of the load-displacement plot as the target outcome^[1-6] but this approach suffers from a lack of uniqueness where different stress-strain curves produce identical load-displacement curves. It has now become clear that using the residual indent profile offers a number of important advantages^[7-10], including alleviating the uniqueness issue.

Other requirements include the need to deform a relatively large volume of material that is representative of the bulk. This requires the effects of all the microstructural features that contribute to the plasticity response to be captured, i.e. the indent must be large relative to the grain size. In addition, the indent must generate relatively large plastic strains to ensure that the range of strains of interest in a conventional tensile test are covered during indentation. There are also a number of important advantages^[3-5, 11, 12] in using a spherical indenter. These include ease of manufacture, reduced risk of damage and a high sensitivity to the detection of anisotropy in the material via a lack of radial symmetry in the indent profile. In terms of practical usage, it is clear that an integrated facility is needed, in which creation of the indent, measurement of its profile and the iterative FEM are under automated software control and are completed within a short period (a few minutes). An example of such a facility is shown in Figure 1. It incorporates a stylus profilometer, has a load capability of about 10 kN and 'uses interchangeable silicon nitride spheres of either 0.5 mm or 1 mm radius. Samples with a yield stress of up to about 2.5 GPa can be tested^[13], with software protection in place to abort any test started on a material with values in excess of this limit. This allows testing of virtually any metal used for structural engineering purposes.

- 1 LED status lights
- 2 Indenter insert (tip and LVDT)
- 3 Load cell
- 4 Sample platform
- 5 Indenter housing
- 6 Profilometer
- 7 Crosshead
- 8 Emergency stop

Figure 1: Image of an indentation plastometer, with the key components labelled.

2. Operation of an Indentation Plastometer

2.1. Basic Operation

The key issues involved in implementation of the PIP procedure are covered in a recent review article^[14]. One point to note is that the elastic constants of the material and the indenter, the Young's modulus and Poisson ratio, are required for the FEM simulation. While the focus is on plasticity, elastic deformation takes place during the test and does affect the outcome (residual indent shape). For the indenter, the elastic constants are defined by the indenter material and for the specimen, the sensitivity to these elastic constants is relatively small and they need only be specified to a precision of about 10–15%. Furthermore, since the modulus is determined by the electrostatic interactions between the atoms in the structure and shows very little sensitivity to microstructure (unlike plasticity, which is strongly influenced by microstructure) all that is required is knowledge of the base metal.

Once the elastic constants have been specified, indentation has been carried out, the profile has been measured and the iterative FEM algorithm has been implemented, the "solution" is obtained as a true stress – true plastic strain relationship, in the form of a set of three parameter values in a constitutive law. For PIP testing, the Voce law is used, as shown in Equation (1) where σ is the (true) stress, ε is the (true) strain, σ_y is the **yield stress**, σ_s is a **saturation stress** and ε_0 is a **characteristic strain** (for the approach of the stress to its saturation level). When implemented in the FEM model, these stresses and strains are **von Mises values**.

$$\sigma = \sigma_s - (\sigma_s - \sigma_y) \exp\left(\frac{-\varepsilon}{\varepsilon_0}\right) \quad (1)$$

Figure 2: Measured and (best-fit) modelled indent profiles^[10], for two penetration depths, for (a) as-received Cu and (b) annealed Cu.

A typical comparison between experimental and best-fit modelled indent profiles is shown in Figure 2 for as-received and annealed copper (with two different penetration depths in each case – i.e. two different applied loads). A corresponding comparison is shown in Figure 3 between the nominal stress – nominal strain plots obtained by tensile testing these materials and those from the indentation-derived true stress – and true strain relationship (with FEM simulation needed to obtain the post-necking part of the curve).

Figure 3: Nominal stress-strain curves from tensile testing of two copper alloys, comparing directly measured plots with those obtained from PIP-derived true stress-strain curves.

2.2. Mapping of Stress-Strain Characteristics

PIP testing offers many advantages over conventional uniaxial testing. These include a capability for the mapping of properties on a relatively fine scale. The deformed region is typically a disk of about 0.5 mm radius and a thickness around 0.2 mm, so mapping on a scale of mm is feasible. An example^[15] is presented in Figure

4, which shows two maps of yield stress and ultimate tensile stress (UTS) across parent-weld transition regions.

Such information cannot be obtained via tensile testing and, while it would be common to carry out hardness tests on this type of scale, hardness numbers are just semi-quantitative indicators of the resistance to plastic deformation and should not be used in any quantitative way. In contrast to this, these PIP-derived stress-strain relationships (as a function of location) can be used in FEM simulation of how the weld region would respond under service conditions.

2.3. Detection of Anisotropy

It is quite common for metallic samples to exhibit at least some (plastic) anisotropy – i.e. for the stress-strain curve to be different when tested in different directions – for example, in the two in-plane directions and the through-thickness direction of a rolled plate. This commonly arises from crystallographic texture – a non-random distribution in the orientations of individual grains. One attraction of PIP is that it has a high sensitivity to the detection of in-plane anisotropy, in the form of a lack of radial symmetry in the indent. Indent profiles are routinely taken in more than one direction and any significant differences between them are automatically flagged to the operator. An example^[16] is shown in Figure 5.

The two SEM micrographs of the indent (in transverse and parallel planes relative to the growth direction of an additively manufactured superalloy component) do show that one of them is not radially symmetric. Rather more sensitively, the profiles are noticeably different for the asymmetrical case, with the pile-up height greater in the “softer” direction – which in this case is the growth direction. The PIP-derived stress-strain curve is effectively a direction-averaged one, lying between those obtained via tensile testing in the two principal directions. Although it is not at present possible to obtain stress-strain curves for different directions from a PIP test, the presence and sense of the anisotropy can be detected. Since the monitoring of anisotropy is often very difficult via uniaxial testing, this is a valuable capability.

Figure 4: PIP-derived outcomes^[15] for the parent-weld transition regions, showing (a) a schematic of the test geometry, (b) a plot of tensile yield stress and UTS against location for Weld 1 and (c) equivalent data for Weld 2.

Figure 5: Information^[16] relating to PIP testing of an additively-manufactured Ni superalloy sample, showing SEMs of (a) transverse and (b) axial sections, corresponding profile scans, (c) and (d) and (e) comparison between stress-strain curves obtained by tensile testing (both directions) and PIP (transverse section only).

3. An Industrial Case Study

3.1. Objectives

It is common for components to have large variation in properties due to their processing. This is widely seen in all industries, for example when large plastic strains are imposed during forming, or when there are localised differences in thermal histories such as near a weld. When the scale of such inhomogeneity is smaller than the scale of a tensile test, such that the variations have little effect, it becomes difficult to fully characterise a component. Often hardness testing would be used instead, but this gives only a semi-quantitative indication of a material's plasticity properties. For the purposes of making confident engineering decisions, such as predicting component life as part of an engineering critical assessment (ECA) where plasticity properties are required, a different method is needed for characterisation, which can give localised plasticity parameters. PIP testing is able to bridge this gap, giving a full stress-strain curve from an indentation-based test, and is therefore ideally suited to characterising parts with localised plastic inhomogeneity. The objective of this case study was to detect localised variations in the plasticity parameters of a section of an aluminium-based forging, pictured in Figure 6. Traditional uniaxial testing, both tensile and compressive, was carried out and compared to PIP testing on a sectioned slice of the forging.

Figure 6: Photo of the Al-based forging.

3.2. Methods

3.2.1. Microstructural Examination

Microstructures were examined using optical and SEM microscopy, with EDX for compositional analysis. An investigation was also made into the phases present, using a Philips X'Pert PW3020 X-ray diffractometer, in combination with the Highscore programme, and the Inorganic Crystal Structure Database (ICSD) was used to identify phases formed on the free surfaces. The Highscore search was limited to phases containing Al, Ni and Fe.

3.2.2. Uniaxial Testing

Uniaxial testing was carried out both in tension and compression for the Al-based forging. Figure 7 shows a photo of a section of the forging, indicating the approximate locations from which tensile and compression samples were cut, and the corresponding numbering system. The numbers for the compression samples are also used to indicate the locations of indents. Round tensile samples were machined in accordance with ASTM E8, and compression samples were 5 mm diameter by 5 mm height. All tests were carried out on an Instron 3367 conventional mechanical testing frame. Full details of the conditions used for tensile and compressive testing are available in previous publications^[5, 10, 17, 18].

3.2.3. PIP Testing

PIP results were measured using a PLX Benchtop Plastometer, pictured in Figure 1. Multiple indents were carried out, and the compression sample locations in Figure 7 give a rough indication of their location. The input Young's modulus of the forging was taken to be 69 GPa, and the Poisson's ratio to be 0.3.

After preparation to P2500 grit using silicon carbide paper, and polishing using 1 μm diamond paste, the sectioned Al-forging was placed on the load cell of the plastometer. A 1 mm diameter indenter ball was used to indent the material in several locations with a fixed load of 1.5 kN. A contacting stylus profilometer, with a depth resolution of about 1 μm , was used to carry out profilometry of the indents.

Tilt correction functions were applied to the raw data, based on the far-field parts of the scan being parallel. Iterative finite element analysis is then applied to obtain the true stress-strain curve, by optimising for three plasticity parameters in a constitutive law. Confidence intervals are also presented based on how unique the experimental residual indent profile is. These procedures are carried out automatically under software control. Comparisons with the uniaxial testing data related to nominal stress v. nominal strain curves, for which simple analytical conversions from the true form were used. These are only valid while the stress and strain fields within the gauge length are uniform, which is the case up to the onset of necking (the UTS).

Figure 7: Photo of sectioned Al-based forging, with a schematic showing the locations of 4 tensile samples and 10 compressive samples.

Figure 8: SEM micrographs of a polished section from the Al-base forging, at (a) low and (b) high magnifications.

	Composition (atomic %)						
	Al	Mg	Si	Fe	Ni	Cu	Ag
Particle	69	-	0.5	14	14	1.5	-
Overall	94	2.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	1.0	1.0

Table 1: Approximate compositions obtained via EDX on the Al-based forging.

3.3. Results and Discussion

3.3.1. Microstructure

The microstructure of the forging was unusual and varied between different locations within the component. The grain structure was relatively fine (~30-150 μm) throughout, although there were certainly local variations in grain size and shape. More striking was the presence of a significant volume fraction (~7 %) of the second phase in the form of relatively coarse (~5-10 μm) precipitates. These showed a strong tendency to: (a) align so that their longer axis is in a particular direction and (b) be collected into parallel sets of “stringers”, as can be seen in Figure 8.

This kind of structure is strongly indicative of the effect of relatively large plastic strains being imposed in the direction concerned. It is likely that the component was produced in a two-stage process, being initially cast to a suitable shape, and then plastically deformed during a forging process, with the magnitude and directionality of the plastic strain varying between different locations.

The composition of the second phase was obtained using EDX in the SEM, with the beam focused on individual particles. The overall average composition of the alloy was obtained similarly, with the beam scanned over a large area. Both sets of compositions are shown in Table I, where it can be seen that the second phase mainly contains Al, Fe and Ni. It was identified by X-ray diffraction as $\text{Fe}_{0.7}\text{Ni}_{1.3}\text{Al}_9$, with a typical spectrum shown in Figure 9. (This phase has a complex crystal structure, giving many low intensity peaks: those at high Bragg angles are virtually impossible to identify, but several at lower angles are indexed in Figure 9 and it seems likely

that only this phase is present, apart from the Al matrix, or other phases present at levels below 1%.) The (relatively low) intensity of the second-phase peaks is consistent with it being present at a level of about 7 vol%.

This alloy is thus effectively a particulate reinforced MMC. The FeNiAl phase is both stiffer and harder than the matrix, so a significant increase in both stiffness and hardness of the material is expected to result from its presence^[18]. Furthermore, the alignment evident in Figure 8(a) is expected to create some (in-plane) anisotropy. In addition, differences in the magnitude of the plastic strain in different parts of the forging are also expected to affect the mechanical properties, with work hardening of the matrix expected to raise the yield stress in parts subjected to higher strains. Care is, however, needed here, since it is possible that recrystallization, leading to marked softening, could have occurred after forging, depending on the thermal history.

There is clearly interest in exploring variations in microstructure between different parts of the forging. Some information of this type can be seen in Figure 10, which shows several optical micrographs, together with an indication of their location on the section shown. The alignment of the FeNiAl precipitates allows the broad nature of the plastic flow field during forging to be visualized, giving at least some idea of the probable distribution of plastic strain. Most regions have clearly been subjected to relatively high strains, although there appears to be a region in the lower central part of the section (near image 27) that may have been a “dead zone” that remained relatively undeformed from the original cast structure.

Figure 9: XRD spectrum from the Al-based forging.

Figure 10: Set of optical micrographs, together with an indication of their locations on the section of the Al-based forging.

Figure 11: (a) Tensile nominal stress-strain curves and (b) compressive nominal stress-strain curves, taken from the locations shown in Fig. 7.

3.3.2. Uniaxial Testing

Tensile stress-strain curves are shown in Figure 11(a), with the labels corresponding to the locations shown in Figure 7. These curves are all very similar, with a yield stress of around 420 MPa and a UTS value of about 450 MPa. It is also evident that there is little or no systematic difference between the individual curves. This is in fact unsurprising in view of the information in Figure 10. While there are certainly indications there that some locations had been subject to different plastic strains during manufacture, these tensile tests were interrogating relatively large volumes of material, over which such local variations would probably have had little effect.

Illustrative compressive stress-strain curves are shown in Figure 11(b). These relate to two pairs of samples, both from the base region, one from a location near the inner surface and one near the outer surface – see Figure 7. Even on the relatively coarse scale of the compression samples, significant variations are apparent. The yield stress is noticeably higher for the outer region (samples 9 and 10), which may be associated with that region having experienced higher prior strains during manufacture. This type of relevant information is lost in the tensile test results of Figure 11(a).

3.3.3. PIP Testing

PIP tests were carried out in different locations, with significant differences between some of the outcomes. Variations were observed from point to point, consistent with observed differences in local microstructure. As an example, derived plots are shown in Figure 12 for two locations, compared in each case with the tensile curves of Figure 11(a). While there are locations for which the indent profiles reflect the tensile test outcomes, and these were in the majority, in other locations the outcome indicated a slightly different response with a higher yield stress. This outcome highlights the capability of PIP testing to obtain stress-strain characteristics on a much finer scale than is possible by conventional tensile or compressive testing.

PIP testing also detected marked anisotropy, although it varied from point to point and was not systematic across the component. The anisotropy in this component does not arise from texture, but from preferential alignment and inhomogeneous distribution of a hard “reinforcement”. It could be regarded as a (metal matrix) composite material and in general composites often exhibit strong anisotropy.

Figure 12: Conventional and PIP-derived tensile stress-strain curves, with the indents located at (a) point 5 and (b) point 9 (as shown in Fig. 7).

Figure 13: SEM micrograph of an indent in the Al-based component.

The kind of effect that can arise during indentation of such material is illustrated by the SEM micrograph of an indent shown in Figure 13. The alignment of the “stringers” in this case is from top left to bottom right. Small “undulations” have been created around the rim of the indent, which are primarily associated with the anisotropy (possibly influenced in some cases by a relatively large grain size in these regions – there is some rotation of individual grains in the rim area during indentation). Variations such as these have the potential to influence measured indent profiles. This is illustrated by Figure 14, which shows four profiles across another indent, oriented at four different angles. Such variations are not normally observed. An average can be taken of such profiles, and this is likely to lead to a direction-

Figure 14: Profiles in four directions across a single indent, in a region exhibiting pronounced anisotropy, due to the presence of strongly aligned “stringers” of hard particles.

averaged stress-strain curve that will be acceptably accurate. However, such variations can already be used to obtain information about local anisotropy, for example the direction parallel to the “stringers” is hardest as its profile has the lowest peak pile-up. In this way, a single indent has identified the presence and sense of

anisotropy, without the need for machining separate samples.

3.3.4. Applications of PIP Testing

The ability to generate accurate stress-strain curves from a simple indentation test opens many applications for PIP testing. As has been shown, it can be used to map properties over inhomogeneous components such as forgings or those containing welds. It can also be used for quality control or quality assurance purposes, as a replacement for tensile testing or hardness testing, as well as for rapid quality checks during manufacture to optimise further processing on the component. The turnaround times are significantly lower than for tensile testing, where the requirement for CNC machining often leads to days or weeks of a delay, and therefore the cost per test is also significantly lower.

As an indentation-based technique, an added advantage is that it can be applied to high-value assets in the field for in-situ monitoring of properties. Applications in this space include the assessment of properties in oil and gas pipelines, especially if such assets are to be repurposed for example for the transport of hydrogen. In this context, it can be used as a non-destructive test method to support engineering critical assessments.

4. Summary

The following points can be noted regarding PIP technology:

- Integrated facilities are now commercially available, with the complete set of operations under automated control, so an understanding of their capabilities and features is starting to become highly significant. It seems likely that usage of the technology will expand considerably over the next few years.
- If “bulk” properties are required, then it is important to mechanically interrogate a “representative” (many-grained) volume, and to create plastic strains in the approximate range of up to several tens of %. These requirements lead, in turn, to a need for an indenter radius of around 0.5–1 mm, a penetration depth of a few hundred μm and a load capability in the kN range.
- Using the profile of the residual indent as the target outcome, rather than the load-displacement plot, offers many advantages. It is easier from an experimental point of view, its sensitivity to the stress-strain curve is greater and it allows detection and exploration of sample anisotropy.
- PIP can be applied to a wide range of industrial scenarios, offering capabilities such as mapping of properties over surfaces and detecting anisotropy. Some examples are presented here. Such information cannot be obtained using conventional uniaxial testing. In addition, the cost of a PIP test is significantly lower and the turnaround time significantly faster than the conventional tensile test where coupons must be prepared through subtractive manufacturing.

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